

Spectrophotometry and Amperometry of the Reaction Product Obtained by Refluxing Cr(III) with Sodium Pyrophosphate

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The composition of chromium pyrophosphate complex formed by the interaction of CrCl_3 and equivalent neutralised sodium pyrophosphate has been studied by spectrophotometry and amperometric titrations. A 3:2 complex corresponding to $\text{Cr} : \text{P}_2\text{O}_7$ has been established. Stability constant of the complex was calculated by molar ratio method (25×10^{12}). The complex was isolated and analysed for chromium(III) phosphorous; and pyrophosphate as a whole according to which 1:1 complex exist NaCrP_2O_7 . The structure of the complex has been confirmed by I. R. spectra.

The earliest reference on this topic is the work of Zhigach and Konstantinova¹ on the chemical analysis of the precipitate obtained by the interaction of chromic chloride and sodium pyrophosphate. Recently a few important papers^{2,3,4} involving the use of Cr(II)-Cr(III) couple in presence of alkali metal pyrophosphate for the reduction of cobalt amines have appeared in the literature. These studies provide indirect evidence for the existence of Cr(III) pyrophosphate but no light has been thrown on the nature and composition of the compound. Investigation in this direction was therefore undertaken employing various physicochemical methods to establish the composition of the complex.

EXPERIMENTAL

Reagents: Sodium pyrophosphate solution was prepared in distilled water containing four equivalents of HCl. Since the solution of sodium pyrophosphate did not remain stable for a long time, fresh solutions were prepared when required.

All other chemicals used were of analytical reagent grade.

Apparatus: O.D. measurements were carried out with the help of Bausch and Lomb's spectronic 20. Infracord Perkin and Elmer (courtesy: director, N. C. L., Poona) was used for recording I.R. spectra. Measurements were made in the Nujol phase.

Amperometric titrations were carried out with the help of Toshniwal Polarograph (India) using scalamp galvanometer (W. G. Pye) in the external circuit. All measurements were carried out at $25 \pm 0.1^\circ$ in the water thermostat. The capillary used has the following characteristics in the open circuit, $t=3.5$ sec.; $m=5.54$ mg/sec⁻¹; $m^{2/3}t^{1/6}=3.88$.

1. K. F. Zhigach and K. V. Konstantinova, *Doklady Akad Nauk S. S. S. R.*, 1955, **104**, 559-62.
2. H. Taube, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1955, **77**, 4481.
3. J. E. Earley and J. H. Gorbuty, *J. Inorg. Nucl. Chem.*, 1963, **25**, (3), 306-7.
4. J. Hunt and J. Earley, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1960, **82**, 5312.

Procedures: Vosburg Copper's method was employed for knowing the number of complexes formed. The plot of optical densities against wave length gave a maximum at 430 μ thereby showing the existence of only one complex (the mixture of chromic chloride and water refluxed under similar conditions gave the maxima at 400 μ). Optical densities were measured in the wave length region 380 μ to 445 μ .

FIG. 1

FIG. 2

The amperometric titrations were all carried out at an applied potential of -1.5V. A series of solutions were made up, each of which contained a different ratio of chromium to pyrophosphate. The total volume was made upto 15 ml. These solutions were refluxed on steam bath and then current was measured at the above potential. The curve was drawn in current against the volume of the titrant added in ml.

The compound was isolated with the help of acetate buffer of pH 4. Both the solutions were mixed and then refluxed. Within few seconds a green precipitate is settled. The precipitate so obtained was filtered and then washed with distilled water until free from chloride ions. The precipitate was dried in desiccator over calcium chloride. The chromium was estimated volumetrically, phosphorous spectrophotometrically⁵ and pyrophosphate ion as a whole was determined by polarographic⁶ methods.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Spectrophotometric studies carried out by Job's⁷ method of continuous variation, molar ratio method⁸ and slope ratio method provide evidence for the existence of a 3:2

5. R. E. Kitson and G. Mellon, *Ind., Eng. Chem., Anal. Ed.* 1944, **16**, 466.

6. G. Cohn and I. M. Kolthoff, *Ind., Eng. Chem., Anal. Edn.* 1942, **14**, 886.

7. *Compt. rend.*, 1925, **180**, 928; *Ann. Chim.*, 1928, **X**, 9, 113.

8. *Idem, ibid.*, 1959, **36**, 285.

complex. The stability constant of the complex was determined by the molar ratio method (fig. 1) which was found to be 25×10^{12} . The value of $-\Delta F$ was 18.2 K. Cals. This ratio was confirmed by amperometric titrations (fig. 2) which were carried out by adding sodium pyrophosphate to chromic chloride (in the polarographic cell).

The I.R. spectrum of the isolated complexes was very informative. Bands at 3509 cm^{-1} and 1672 cm^{-1} indicated the presence of OH deformation mode. The evidence for the presence of P-O-P, was obtained from the bands near 900 cm^{-1} and also near 700 cm^{-1} . Corbridge and Lowe¹⁰ as well as Harvey and Maywood¹¹ suggested these absorption region for P_2O_7 group.

FIG. 3

The results obtained after the analysis of the isolated complex were in favour of 1 : 1 complex.

The reaction was only possible when the solutions were refluxed at 80° for about 3 hrs. At room temperature there was no reaction. The free energy change for the reaction is directly related to the stability constant of the Cr(III) complex formed by the reaction. There was evidences that P_2O_7 ion forms most stable complexes with +3 ions than does PO_4 .

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10. Corbridge and Lowe, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1954, 493.
11. Harvey and Maywood, *Can. J. Chem.*, 1955, 33, 1552.